

Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: A Logically Paradoxical Picture

Amir Abbass Varshovi*

Abstract: The many-worlds interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics is studied with a logical argumentation based on the existence of semi-deterministic parallel worlds in the interpretation. An endless ensemble of infinite copies of a specific quantum state is considered for implementing a certain measurement. It is shown that the set of parallel worlds created by the consecutive observations is theoretically identical to the unit segment $[0, 1]$, wherein the rational numbers represent the parallel worlds in which Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is thoroughly refuted. Despite being of a Lebesgue measure null set such a bizarre collection of parallel worlds practically exists in the ontology of the MWI and has infinite elements. We will establish that this existence creates an inherent paradoxical picture in the MWI. By studying the analytical details of the mentioned collection and evaluating the improvement or refutation of the existence of the present world where we live from the scientific insight of the sentient beings of the other parallel worlds it is established that an inevitable consequence of the MWI is that the world where we live is an unreal illusion.

Keywords: Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics, Semi-Deterministic Worlds, Reference Worlds, Logical Values.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics that Hugh Everett proposed in the 1950s [1][2], and was popularized by Bryce DeWitt during the 1970s [3][4] is, in principle, a deterministic theory that tries to figure out the role of measurement in theoretical/empirical aspects of quantum physics by introducing parallel worlds [5]. It is mostly believed to be the most extraordinary, captivating, and thought-provoking of all how quantum mechanics has been interpreted. In other words, the MWI is in essence distinct from the other interpretations of quantum mechanics, since it, in fact, speaks about the meaning of knowledge and reality in science [6]. However, there are several explanations of the MWI¹ but they all have one idea in common: The collapse postulate can be removed from the axioms of quantum mechanics [18]. Indeed, the MWI endeavors to avoid the complication of wavefunction collapse but at the expense of making another parallel world, and for some physicists it sounds like a mesmerizing exegesis of the problem, not a real solution.

However, the MWI's primary and most well-known flaw is that it cannot be tested and approved with current or anticipated experimental capabilities.² In fact, even some physicists who support the

*Electronic address: ab.varshovi@sci.ui.ac.ir/amirabbassv@gmail.com/amirabbassv@ipm.ir

¹ See [8][2][10][17][9][11][13][14][15][7][12][16] for such interpretations.

² See [20][6][19][9][16][10] and the references therein for more discussion about this problem.

interpretation are not confident about the theoretical underpinnings of the MWI's testability [10]. Actually, in addition to the confusion about the testability of the MWI, it has encountered several intellectual/theoretical criticisms the most notable ones are the well-known philosophical objection due to the law of parsimony or Occam's razor principle,³ the ontological puzzle and the insufficiency of the Universe wavefunction,⁴ the trouble of the incoherence of the probabilities and the role of the Born rule in the interpretation,⁵ and the problem of ill-defined preferred basis.⁶ Moreover, it seems that the MWI is an incomplete theory as it doesn't provide a satisfactory explanation for the measurement problem in quantum mechanics.⁷ The main problem about this incompleteness, as some physicists believe, is that the MWI was proposed to overcome the problem of the measurement postulate of quantum mechanics, however, after discarding this postulate, the MWI requires another succeeding principle, that brings the measurement problem back. All in all, the MWI of quantum mechanics suffers from various theoretical/empirical defects.⁸

In essence, MWI is sometime believed to be more of a philosophical interpretation than a testable physical theory.⁹ But is this philosophical interpretation logically consistent and free of structural contradictions? In other words, does the ontological picture of the MWI provide a reliable framework for understanding the fundamental problems in quantum physics including the essence and details of the mechanism of measurement? In this paper, we will study the integrity and the consistency of the MWI from this prospect. We will show that beside the mentioned problems, the MWI has an inherent logical paradox and, hence is a false and unreliable interpretation. Indeed, we will prove that assuming infinitely many unapprovable parallel worlds as physical facts leads to the illusory nature of our own world. In other words, assuming the MWI as a correct interpretation has an inevitable logical consequence which asserts that the present world where we live is an unphysical picture and, hence an illusion.

II. MANY-WORLDS INTERPRETATION: ILLUSTRATIVE OR SEDUCTIVE

Unpredictability is one of the main consequences of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. In other words, Heisenberg's uncertainty principle guarantees that the outcome of the observation of a physical quantity of a superposition state will not follow any specific predictable pattern. We will show that this understanding of the uncertainty principle will lead to a contradiction with the MWI of quantum mechanics, hence proves that the MWI is a paradoxical picture.

To demonstrate the promised conclusion we have to design a gedanken experiment in quantum mechanics. Let $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|0\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|1\rangle$ be a superposition state of an electron, where $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are respectively the states of up and down spins along the z -axis, which we simply refer to as the *electron*

³ See [23][21][22] for more commentaries on the problem.

⁴ See [26][25][19][24][20] and the references therein for more discussions on supporting or refuting the ontology of the MWI.

⁵ See [30][20][28][29][27][31] for the critique and the reply.

⁶ See [33][32][34][20] for details of the problem and the discussions on defending or rejecting the possible solutions.

⁷ See for example [35].

⁸ See also [38][41][42][36][47][44][46][50][15][43][6][40][48][49][45][21][39][37] for more discussions about the problems of the MWI.

⁹ See [51][52][20][6][19][53][54] for more discussions about philosophical features of the MWI.

z-spins. Assume that \mathcal{A} is an endless ensemble that consists of infinite copies of $|\psi\rangle$, each of which is labeled by a natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Based on the MWI each observation of the *z*-spin of the elements of \mathcal{A} splits the present world to two parallel branches. Therefore, accomplishing the total observations (if possible) will produce uncountable parallel worlds, each of which is characterized by a unique infinite sequence consisting of 0 and 1, where the appearance of 0 (resp. 1) as the n -th element of the sequence means observing $|0\rangle$ (resp. $|1\rangle$) at the n -th experiment.

Suppose that ω is a parallel world and $\{a_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is its sequence. This sequence can be rewritten as a real number in base 2 as

$$s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3 \cdots . \quad (\text{II.1})$$

Here, along with this study for the sake of technical reasons, we will add an augmented condition to (II.1) as below:

C*: *We will omit parallel worlds whose sequences terminate with infinite 1s except $1 = 0.111 \cdots$.*

This precision is considered because some real numbers do not have unique representations, for example, $0.a_1 \cdots a_n 1000 \cdots$, and $0.a_1 \cdots a_n 0111 \cdots$, show the same point in $[0, 1]$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and any collection of $a_1, \cdots, a_n \in \{0, 1\}$. We will assume **C*** to be considered in (II.1) for the subsequent discussions and argumentations. Therefore, any parallel world is depicted with a unique point in $[0, 1]$. On the other hand, each real number in the closed interval $[0, 1]$ has a unique expansion in base 2 just similar to (II.1) as far as **C*** is assumed. Thus, mathematically the observations of \mathcal{A} will produce all the numbers of $[0, 1]$. We will refer to s_ω as the *world's code*. In other words, the world's codes are unique representations of the real numbers in $[0, 1]$ such as (II.1) so that the digits do not terminate with infinite 1s except for $1 = 0.111 \cdots$.

The world's codes are separated into two distinct groups: **1)** rational numbers, and **2)** irrational numbers. The two groups have too many distinctions but the most significant for our aim of study is that *the sequence of digits of any element of the former group obey ultimately a definite pattern, hence are predictable* [55]. In other words, if $s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3 \cdots$ is a rational number there exist some $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ so that $a_{n+km+r} = a_{n+r}$ for all $k \geq 1$ and $m \geq r \geq 1$. More precisely, s_ω belongs to \mathbb{Q} if and only if we have:

$$s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3 \cdots = 0.b_1 \cdots b_n c_1 \cdots c_m c_1 \cdots c_m c_1 \cdots c_m c_1 \cdots c_m \cdots , \quad (\text{II.2})$$

where in $b_i, c_j \in \{0, 1\}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq j \leq m$.

Consequently, if the world's code s_ω is a rational number, then the observer of the parallel world ω discovers a deterministic law for the observations and, hence will not confirm the uncertainty principle in *z*spin measurements for \mathcal{A} . By employing some arrangements we can readily assume that \mathcal{A} is the collection of all electron *z*-spin experiments in the history of the world. Thus, the parallel worlds with rational s_ω experience a deterministic law for the electron *z*-spin observations. Based on this fact, we call them *semi-deterministic worlds* and refer to their agents as *semi-deterministic observers*. Similarly, a parallel world with an irrational code is called a *reference world* while its sentient beings, who confirm the uncertainty principle in *z*-spin observations are known as *reference observers*. Therefore, our present world (at this moment) is a reference world which we will denote it by ω_0 .

If we assume that the natural phenomena outside the laboratory are the same for both semi-deterministic and reference worlds, then the physical knowledge of a semi-deterministic observer is incomplete for explaining the quantum physics of nature. In principle, the observer's physical knowledge is his only source for confirming or refuting the possible existence of other parallel worlds. More precisely, it is obvious that a semi-deterministic observer gives no chance for the existence of ω_0 , since he believes in a deterministic physical law in observations of electron z -spins. For instance, the parallel worlds ω_m and ω_M with worlds's codes $s_{\omega_m} = 0$ and $s_{\omega_M} = 1 = 0.111\cdots$ would conclude that ω_0 is completely an unphysical imagination, since they will observe only one specific value for the electron z -spin. It is the same conclusion that the sentient beings in the zig-zag parallel world ω_z with $s_{\omega_z} = 0.010101\cdots$ will obtain since they believe in an iterating physical law in observations of the electron z -spin and, hence reject the uncertainty principle in this case. All in all, a semi-deterministic observer asserts the following proposition:

Proposition 1; *The existence of the parallel world ω_0 is physically impossible. Hence, ω_0 is an unreal illusion.*

Now, our main scientific endeavor is to determine whether the **Proposition 1** is logically "False" or "True". To do this within a consistent way we assume a definite real-valued function f on $[0, 1]$, the so-called *validity function*, which assigns to the world's code of a parallel world the logical value that its sentient beings will give to the **Proposition 1**, where the logical value of "False" is 0 and that of "True" is 1. However, for simplicity and paving the way for some theoretical considerations such as assuming a continuum range for logical values, we can let f take its image in $[0, 1]$. Hence, we readily define $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$. Moreover, upon the above argumentations we must have $f(s_\omega) = 1$ for any semi-deterministic world ω . That is f must satisfy the following property:

Property 1) $f(s_\omega) = 1$ for all rational numbers $s_\omega \in [0, 1]$.

Actually, f is a function related to scientific judgments. However, scientific judgments are made based on the statistics (the history) of extremely high but finite numbers of observations. On the other hand, the digits of any world's code describe the history of observations in that parallel world. Thus, the larger the set of common initial digits two parallel worlds' codes have, the longer the common history/statistics of observations they have had.¹⁰ More precisely, the closer the two world's codes are to each other in $[0, 1]$, the more common physical knowledge their sentient beings will have. Hence, the closer s_{ω_1} and s_{ω_2} are to each other, the more similar scientific judgments the sentient beings of the parallel worlds ω_1 and ω_2 will make about any asserted proposition. Therefore, the closer s_{ω_1} and s_{ω_2} are to each other, the closer $f(s_{\omega_1})$ and $f(s_{\omega_2})$ are. In other words, f must fulfill another condition:

Property 2) $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous function.

The two properties **Property 1** and **Property 2** have a definite mathematical solution which

¹⁰ The augmented condition **C*** for (II.1) ensures the validity of this statement.

states that f is a constant function, i.e. $f(s_\omega) = 1$ for all $s_\omega \in [0, 1]$. Consequently, we conclude that $f(\omega_0) = 1$ which is a scientifically bizarre and obviously invalid conclusion meaning that the sentient beings of the present world must confirm that their world is an unreal illusion by approving **Proposition 1**. However, despite the obvious invalidity of the mentioned assertion, it is, as we proved above, an inevitable consequence of the MWI of quantum mechanics. More precisely, if the MWI is a true interpretation of quantum mechanics, then the semi-deterministic observers' judgment that ω_0 is an unreal world would be scientifically an authentic claim.

It seems that the above logical calamity stems from a fundamental contradiction of the assumptions of the MWI which produces parallel worlds whose sentient beings reject the postulates of quantum mechanics, and hence the MWI itself. The mentioned argumentation shows that although the MWI brings up the branching process and creating the parallel worlds it cannot guarantee the transfer of information, and consequently the understanding of physical laws to the separated worlds and their sentient beings. In other words, the MWI will produce parallel worlds whose sentient beings will gradually (statistically) lose their belief in the MWI and confirm a (semi-) deterministic law for some specific quantum mechanical measurements. Thus, it seems that the MWI unintendedly destroys the validity of physical laws by creating unphysical worlds, and this flaw ultimately emerges as a logical contradiction in the interpretation.

More precisely, the main problem of the MWI is that its ontology has no limits and, hence, contains parallel worlds whose sentient beings disapprove of the MWI itself. This is, in fact, a reminiscence of Russell's paradox. We remind that Russell's paradox shows that every set theory that contains an unrestricted comprehension principle leads to contradictions [56]. Therefore, since the set of the promised ontology of the MWI admits no restriction it would likely suffer from an inherent paradoxical loop from its inside just similar to the reported defect of set theory pointed out by Russell. What we did in the above arguments was intrinsically inspired by Russell's approach. We tried to take advantage of the endless breadth of the MWI ontology and discover a hidden contradiction within this staggering enormity. Based on Russell's experience we expected that since any possibility is allowed in the ontology of the MWI, the interpretation will face an inherent negation in its mathematical/logical foundations.

Strictly speaking, the MWI bestows the credit of physical reality to all subjective possibilities and probable histories of quantum mechanical observations including obviously unrealistic parallel worlds, and the number of such unphysical worlds is so vast that the proposed interpretation encounters an inherently logical contradiction from the inside. In other words, the MWI allows the creation of infinitely many unrealistic parallel worlds at the closest distance from any physical world (from the topological point of view we introduced above), and the statistical information of these worlds are so close to each other that will affect their mutual understanding of the laws of physics. This topological closeness of parallel worlds from the ontological point of view means the closeness of understanding of their sentient beings of physical reality. This merger of real and unreal pictures is what destroys MWI from the inside. This argumentation is a detailed description of the paradox that was examined above from a mathematical perspective via the validity function f .

Basically, the definition of the validity function f and its properties, especially its continuity, is an inevitable consequence of the MWI assumptions about the reality of all possible parallel worlds including unphysical ones. We can talk about the decisions of sentient beings about the validity of a

scientific statement only when they have the ability of contemplation and recognition, and this requires the indispensable demand of their physical existence. Hence, the definition of the validity function f inherently depends on the reliability of the presumptions of the MWI. In addition, the continuity of f stems also from the same footings in the foundations of the MWI: To make similar/close decisions based on similar/close histories of observations two sentient beings have to have the power to contemplate and analyze the statistical information of the outcomes, and this ability needs physical existence in the first step.

Therefore, as we can see, the MWI suffers from its own assumptions. It produces infinitely many parallel worlds without any constraints in their physical reality and then it cannot control the emergent chaos of physical and unphysical pictures of quantum mechanics and their merger. This defect of the MWI shows that the interpretation must be revisited from its fundamental assumptions and needs an inevitable reconsideration of its ontological aspects. Strictly speaking, the interpretation to survive must at least provide a limitation on its ontological presumptions to reject the existence of unphysical parallel worlds and bring up a smaller and controllable picture of quantum mechanical possibilities. Otherwise, we must be alert that the interpretation includes an inherent contradiction in its intrinsic structure, which will weaken its capability and reliability in scientific discourses.

Inspired by the usual strategy in set theory, perhaps a simple solution to solve the MWI problem is to define a concept called *small ontology*. This means that MWI ontology should be restricted in accepting all possible parallel worlds. One feasible solution to control the boundless ontology of the interpretation is to introduce some consistent fusion mechanisms between parallel worlds so that a group of them will merge under some specific conditions and produce a unit parallel world. Another solution can be inspired by Darwin's theory of natural selection, such that unphysical parallel worlds whose sentient beings disapprove of physical laws such as Heisenberg's uncertainty principle or the Born rule must extinct after a while.¹¹ The physical process of this extinction can be similar to the decay of unstable quantum particles.

A third solution is to distinguish between mathematical and physical interpretations of existence. In this way, the role of unphysical parallel worlds in advancing quantum mechanical processes is similar to that of off-shell quantum particles in quantum field theory: They exist in the mathematical framework of the theory and play an important role in deriving theoretical/experimental results, but are never observed in the laboratory. In this way, unphysical worlds will exist only in theoretical limits and help to complete the mathematical structure of the theory. In other words, as an elementary particle shows an objective reality in the laboratory only when it is on-shell, a parallel world will have the physical reality only when it obeys the fundamental laws of quantum mechanics including Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and the Born rule.

In any case, either the MWI must be discarded thoroughly or its ontology should be restricted by a consistent scientific method and the three above-mentioned solutions can offer workable approaches toward this end. In other words, the MWI in its current structure is either an inconsistent or perhaps an incomplete theory. Trusting in its conclusions in the present formulation of the interpretation is a highly risky decision and citing it in scientific dialogues is not reliable. The inherent contradiction

¹¹ See [57] for a similar idea to reconcile the aspects of the classical world ontology and the superposition principle of quantum mechanics.

of the MWI is hardly similar to the set theory's paradox revealed by Russell. Thus, it seems that its solution must be similar to the strategy that mathematicians utilize for set theory by introducing small categories. All in all, MWI is a misinterpretation of quantum mechanics and needs serious modifications in its logical foundations of ontological aspects.

III. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we studied the MWI of quantum mechanics from a logical viewpoint. We provided a gedanken experiment for producing infinitely many parallel worlds by measuring the electron z -spin of an endless ensemble that consists of infinite copies of a definite wavefunction. By studying the mathematical structure of this huge collection of parallel worlds and the history of observations in those ones which statistically reject Heisenberg's uncertainty principle we proved that an inevitable consequence of the MWI is that the present world where we live is an unreal illusion. Given this contradictory result, we conclude that the MWI provides a false interpretation of quantum mechanics and needs an indispensable reconsideration of its foundations. We argued that this paradox emerges from a fundamental flaw in the assumptions of the MWI since they will produce infinitely many parallel worlds as physical pictures whose sentient beings gradually disapprove the MWI itself.

-
- [1] Everett H, (1956), *Theory of the Universal Wavefunction*, Thesis, Princeton University.
 - [2] Everett H, (1957), *Relative State Formulation of Quantum Mechanics*, Review of Modern Physics, vol. 29, no. 3: 454-462.
 - [3] DeWitt CM, Wheeler JA (Eds.), (1968), *The Everett-Wheeler Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics*, Battelle Rencontres: 1967, Lectures in Mathematics and Physics.
 - [4] DeWitt BS, (1972), *The Many-Universes Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics*, Proceedings of the International School of Physics, *Enrico Fermi* Course IL: Foundations of Quantum Mechanics, Academic Press.
 - [5] Everett H, Wheeler JA, DeWitt BS, Cooper LN, van Vechten D, Graham N, (1973), *The Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics*, B. S. DeWitt, and Graham, R. Neill (Eds.), Princeton University Press.
 - [6] Ball P, (2018), *Beyond Weird: Why Everything You Thought You Knew about Quantum Physics Is Different*, University of Chicago.
 - [7] Carroll SM, Sebens CT, (2014), *Many Worlds, the Born Rule, and Self-Locating Uncertainty*, in: Y. A. Festschrift, *Quantum Theory: A Two-Time Success Story*, Springer, pages: 157-169.
 - [8] Crease RP, (2019), *The Allure of Many Worlds*, Nature, Vol. 573: 30-32.
 - [9] Deutsch D, (1985), *Quantum Theory as a Universal Physical Theory*, International Journal of Theoretical Physics, vol. 24, no. 1: 1-41.
 - [10] DeWitt BS, (1970), *Quantum Mechanics and Reality*, Physics Today. vol. 23, no. 9: 30-35.
 - [11] Hartle JB, (1991), *Spacetime Coarse Grainings in Nonrelativistic Quantum Mechanics*, Physics Review D, vol. 44, no. 10: 3173.
 - [12] List C, (2023), *The Many-Worlds Theory of Consciousness*, Noûs, vol. 57, no.2: 316-340.
 - [13] Lockwood M, (1996), *Many Minds Interpretations of Quantum Mechanics*, British Journal of Philosophy of Science, vol. 47, no. 2: 159-188.

- [14] Rovelli C, (1996), *Relational Quantum Mechanics*, International Journal of Theoretical Physics, vol. 35, no. 8: 1637-1678.
- [15] Saunders S, Wallace D, (2008), *Branching and Uncertainty*, British Journal of Philosophy of Science, vol. 59: 293-305.
- [16] Vaidman L, (2018), *Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics*, The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy.
- [17] Zeh HD, (1970), *On the Interpretation of Measurement in Quantum Theory*, Foundations of Physics, vol. 1: 69-76.
- [18] Hossenfelder S, (2023), *Quantum Confusions, Cleared Up (or so I Hope)*, arXiv:2309.12299 [quant-ph].
- [19] Bell JS, (1987), *Speakable and Unspeakable in Quantum Mechanics*, Cambridge University Press.
- [20] Kent A, (1990), *Against Many-Worlds Interpretations*, International Journal of Modern Physics, vol. 5, no. 9: 1745-1762. (Also, see [arXiv:gr-qc/9703089v1])
- [21] Gisin N, (2013), *Are There Quantum Effects Coming from Outside Space-time? Nonlocality, Free Will, and “No Many-Worlds”*, in: Suarez A, Adams P (Eds.), *Is Science Compatible with Free Will? Exploring Free Will and Consciousness in the Light of Quantum Physics and Neuroscience*, Springer, New York, pp. 23-39.
- [22] Krizek, GC, (2017), *Ockham’s Razor and the Interpretations of Quantum Mechanics*, arXiv:1701.06564 [quant-ph].
- [23] Zeilinger A, (2004), *Einsteins Schleier: Die neue Welt der Quantenphysik*, C. H. Beck.
- [24] Allori V, Goldstein S, Tumulka R, Zanghi N, (2014), *Predictions and Primitive Ontology in Quantum Foundations: A Study of Examples*, British Journal of Philosophy of Science, doi:10.1093/bjps/axs048.
- [25] Carroll S, (2019), *Something Deeply Hidden: Quantum Worlds and the Emergence of Spacetime*, Oneworld.
- [26] Del Santo F, Gisin N, (2023), *Potentiality Realism: A Realistic and Indeterministic Physics Based on Propensities*, arXiv:2305.02429 [quant-ph].
- [27] Dawid R, Friederich S,(2022), *Epistemic Separability and Everettian Branches: A Critique of Sebens and Carroll*, British Journal of Philosophy of Science, vol. 73, no. 3: 711-721.
- [28] Kent A, (2010), *One World Versus Many: The Inadequacy of Everettian Accounts of Evolution, Probability, and Scientific Confirmation*, in: Saunders S, Barrett J, Kent A, Wallace D (Eds.), *Many Worlds? Everett, Quantum Theory and Reality*, Oxford University Press, pages: 307-354.
- [29] Kent A, (2015), *Does it Make Sense to Speak of Self-Locating Uncertainty in the Universal Wave Function? Remarks on Sebens and Carroll*, Foundation of Physics, vol. 45: 211-217.
- [30] Landsman NP, (2008), *The Born Rule and Its Interpretation*, in: Weinert F, Hentschel K, Greenberger D, Falkenburg B (Eds.), *Compendium of Quantum Physics*, Springer, pages: 64-70.
- [31] Wallace D, (2003), *Everettian Rationality: Defending Deutsch’s Approach to Probability in the Everett interpretation*, Studies in History and Philosophy of Modern Physics, vol. 34: 415-438.
- [32] Dawid R, Thebault KPY, (2015), *Many Worlds: Decoherent or Incoherent?*, Synthese, 192: 1559-1580.
- [33] Hemmo M, Shenker O, (2022), *The Preferred Basis Problem in the Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: Why Decoherence Does Not Solve It*, Synthese, 200(3), Article 261.
- [34] Wallace D, (2010), *Decoherence and Ontology (Or: How I Learned to Stop Worrying and Love FAPP)*, In: *Many Worlds? Everett, Quantum Theory, and Reality*, Saunders S, Barrett J, Kent A, Wallace D (Eds.), Oxford University Press, pp. 53-72.
- [35] Hance JR, Hossenfelder S, (2022), *What Does It Take to Solve the Measurement Problem?*, Journal of Physics Communications, vol. 6, no. 10: 102001.
- [36] Albert D, (2010), *Probability in the Everett Picture*, In: *Many Worlds? Everett, Quantum Theory, and Reality*, Saunders S, Barrett J, Kent A, Wallace D (Eds.), Oxford University Press, pp. 355-368.
- [37] Allori V, (2023), *Many-Worlds: Why Is It Not the Consensus?*, Quantum Reports, vol. 5, no. 1: 80-101.
- [38] Barbado LC, Del Santo F, (2023), *On Playing Gods: The Fallacy of the Many-Worlds Interpretation*,

- arXiv:2311.03467 [physics.hist-ph].
- [39] Barrett JA, (2017), *Typical Worlds*, Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part B: Studies in History and Philosophy of Modern Physics, vol. 58: 31-40.
 - [40] Bub J, (2018), *In Defense of A "Single-World" Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics*, Studies in History and Philosophy of Modern Physics, doi.org/10.1016/j.shpsb.2018.03.002.
 - [41] Derzet A, (2021), *Collapse of the Many-Worlds Interpretation: Why Everett's Theory is Typically Wrong*, arXiv:2109.10646v1 [quant-ph].
 - [42] Gisin N, (2022), *The Multiverse Pandemic*, arXiv:2210.05377 [physics.hist-ph].
 - [43] Hawthorne J, (2010), *A Metaphysician Looks at the Everett Interpretation*, in: Saunders S, Barrett J, Kenet A, Wallace D (Eds.), *Many Worlds? Everett, Quantum Theory, and Reality?*, Oxford University Press, pages: 144-153.
 - [44] Healey R, (1984), *On the Physical Significance of the Locality Conditions in the Bell Arguments*, Noûs, vol. 18: 591.
 - [45] Maudlin T, (2010), *Can the World be Only Wavefunction?*, in: Saunders S, Barrett J, Kenet A, Wallace D (Eds.), *Many Worlds? Everett, Quantum Theory, and Reality?*, Oxford University Press, pages: 121-143.
 - [46] Shimony A, (1986), *Events and Processes in the Quantum World*, (Appendix) in: Penrose R, Isham C (Eds.), *Quantum Concepts in Space and Time*, Clarendon Press, Oxford.
 - [47] Stein H, (1984), *The Everett Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: Many Worlds or None?*, Noûs, vol. 18, 4: 635-652.
 - [48] von Neumann J, (1955), *Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Mechanics*, Princeton University Press, Translated by Robert T. Beyer.
 - [49] Wallace D, (2012), *The Emergent Multiverse: Quantum Theory According to the Everett Interpretation*, Oxford University Press.
 - [50] Wheeler J, (1977), *Include the Observer in the Wave Function?*, in: Lopes JL, Paty M (Eds.), *Quantum Mechanics, Half a Century Later*, Reidel, Dordrecht.
 - [51] Barret JA, Byrne P, (2012), *The Everett Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: Collected Works 1955-1980 with Commentary*, Princeton University Press.
 - [52] Becker L, (2004), *That von Neumann did not Believe in a Physical Collapse*, British Journal of Philosophy of Science, vol. 55: 121-135.
 - [53] Saunders S, Barrett J, Kenet A, Wallace D (Eds.), (2010), *Many Worlds? Everett, Quantum Theory, and Reality?*, Oxford University Press.
 - [54] Tegmark M, (1998), *The Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: Many Worlds or Many Words?*, Fortschritte der Physik, vol. 46: 855-862.
 - [55] Havil J, (2012), *The Irrationals: A Story of the Numbers You Can't Count On*, Princeton University Press.
 - [56] Russell B, (1996), *The Principles of Mathematics*, 2nd Ed., W. W. Norton & Company, 1996.
 - [57] Zurek WH, (2009), *Quantum Darwinism*, Natural Physics, vol. 5: 181-188.